

Personal Protective Equipment Utilization and Occupational Safety Culture among University Cleaners: Implications for Sustainable Health and Decent Work in a Selected Nigeria University

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Abstract:

Cleaners play critical roles in maintaining institutional hygiene, yet face significant occupational hazards, making personal protective equipment (PPE) essential for their safety. Despite global evidence of poor PPE use among non-clinical workers, no empirical study has specifically investigated cleaners in Nigerian universities. This study aimed to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of PPE use among cleaners at Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, and identify factors influencing their utilization. A descriptive qualitative design was employed, involving in-depth interviews with 17 female cleaners selected through purposive convenience sampling from various work areas including hostels, classrooms, laboratories, and administrative blocks. Data were analysed using Braun and Clarke's six-step thematic analysis framework, guided by the Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) model, Health Belief Model (HBM), and Neuman's Systems Model. Results revealed that cleaners held overwhelmingly positive attitudes toward PPE, viewing it as essential despite occasional environmental discomfort. All participants (100%) demonstrated clear understanding of PPE and correctly identified gloves and face masks as essential items. Practice was generally consistent for high-risk tasks such as toilet cleaning, though selective use occurred during perceived lower-risk activities like outdoor sweeping. Key influencing factors included monthly training sessions, unannounced supervisory monitoring, and organizational enforcement policies as enablers, while supply limitations particularly for nose masks and environmental discomfort served as barriers. While knowledge and attitudes were strong, practice gaps existed due to supply limitations and task-based risk perception.

Keywords: Knowledge, Attitude, Practice, Personal Protective Equipment, Cleaners, Occupational health, University,

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Introduction

Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) refers to specialized clothing or equipment worn by workers to minimize exposure to workplace hazards such as infectious agents, chemicals, and physical injuries (Occupational Safety and Health Administration [OSHA], 2023; World Health Organization [WHO], 2024). The correct and consistent use of PPE is widely recognized as a cornerstone of infection prevention and control (IPC), alongside hand hygiene, safe waste disposal, and environmental sanitation (WHO, 2024).

Globally, the importance of PPE became more visible during the COVID-19 pandemic, where shortages and inconsistent use contributed to widespread occupational exposures among healthcare and non-healthcare workers. The crisis underscored that PPE is essential not only for frontline clinical staff but also for support workers who handle cleaning, sanitation, and waste management tasks (Centres for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2024a).

Occupational health and safety frameworks emphasize that all categories of workers including cleaners are entitled to safe working environments. Cleaners play a critical role in maintaining hygienic surroundings through tasks such as surface sanitation, waste collection, and biohazard handling. These responsibilities expose them to contaminated surfaces, sharps, bioaerosols, harsh cleaning chemicals, and other hazards. Without adequate PPE, cleaners are at increased risk of work-related infections, skin irritation, eye injuries, respiratory illnesses, and chemical burns (OSHA, 2023; WHO, 2024). Evidence from low- and middle-income countries consistently shows that while many cleaners demonstrate some awareness of PPE, actual utilization remains suboptimal. A recent study in Eastern Ethiopia found that less than half of sanitary workers consistently used PPE, citing irregular supply, lack of supervision, and gaps in training as contributing factors (Tolera et al., 2024). Similarly, Kigozi and colleagues (2024) reported that although cleaners at a Ugandan national referral hospital expressed positive attitudes toward safety, only a fraction adhered to daily PPE practices. A study in Ethiopia further revealed a disconnect between cleaners' knowledge and practical application of OHS principles (Gebreyessus, 2022).

The Nigerian context reflects similar challenges. Occupational safety policies and training programs often focus predominantly on clinical personnel, leaving non-clinical support staff such as cleaners marginalized in health and safety interventions. On university campuses, cleaners provide indispensable services in lecture halls, hostels, laboratories, and administrative offices, yet their occupational risks are seldom highlighted in policy discourse. At Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, cleaners are central to maintaining sanitary conditions for staff and students, yet preliminary observations suggest PPE use may be inconsistent.

Various factors have been linked to increased risk of occupational exposure among cleaners, including inadequate knowledge of PPE types, limited access to supplies, poor supervisory monitoring, and environmental factors such as heat that discourage consistent use (Sharma et al., 2022). Studies show that cleaners with prior occupational health training are more likely to use PPE correctly (Kigozi et al., 2024). Furthermore, institutional factors such as organizational policies and regular supervisory monitoring improve compliance rates (Ilesanmi et al., 2023). In many developing regions, knowledge and awareness of PPE among non-clinical workers remain low, influenced by limited training opportunities, resource constraints, and organizational neglect (Philippe et al., 2022). Many cleaners perceive their work as low-risk compared to healthcare workers, leading to complacency in PPE use (Bakare & Onwuegbuchu, 2024). Studies show that workplace health education and training play a key role in increasing awareness and improving safety outcomes (Gebreyessus, 2022).

At Al-Hikmah University in Ilorin, a noticeable knowledge gap exists among cleaners regarding proper PPE utilization. This gap may be influenced by training adequacy, institutional policies, supply chain effectiveness, and working conditions (International Labour Organization [ILO], 2022). Understanding their level of knowledge, attitudes toward PPE, actual practices, and the factors that enable or hinder consistent use can improve occupational safety and reduce work-related health complications. Therefore, this study seeks to assess the knowledge, attitudes, and practices of PPE use among cleaners at Al-Hikmah University and identify the factors that influence PPE utilization

This descriptive cross-sectional study focuses on cleaners employed at Al-Hikmah University Adeta campus Ilorin, Kwara State, Nigeria. It assesses the knowledge, attitudes, and practice of PPE use, and explores contextual factors influencing utilization among cleaners working in hostels, classrooms, laboratories, administrative buildings, and other facilities on campus.

Materials and Methods

This study employed a descriptive cross-sectional research design with a qualitative orientation. A descriptive cross-sectional design was appropriate because it allowed assessment of knowledge, attitudes, and practices of PPE among cleaners at a single point in time. The qualitative orientation provided deeper insights into participants' perceptions, attitudes, and contextual factors influencing PPE use. Data were collected through in-depth interviews with selected cleaners of Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin. The target population consisted of all cleaners employed at Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin, Adeta campus. According to administrative records, 53 cleaners were distributed across hostels, academic blocks, laboratories, administrative blocks, the university clinic, library, mosque, and other service units. A purposive convenience sample of 17 participants was selected. Data saturation in qualitative studies is typically achieved with 12 to 20 participants (Guest et al., 2006).

Purposive convenience sampling was used to select 17 participants for in-depth interviews based on their willingness to participate and availability. The limitation of convenience sampling is potential bias, but this was mitigated by selecting cleaners across different facilities to ensure diverse perspectives. Eligible participants were cleaners who had worked for at least 6 months and were actively engaged in cleaning duties. A semi-structured interview guide was developed from the literature review and research objectives, consisting of open-ended questions exploring cleaners' knowledge of PPE types and purposes, attitudes toward PPE use, actual practices and frequency of utilization, and contextual factors affecting compliance. The semi-structured format ensured consistency while allowing flexibility for follow-up questions.

The interview guide was reviewed by the research supervisor to ensure face and content validity. Face validity was ensured by expert review and pre-testing with 2 cleaners not included in the main study. For qualitative studies, reliability is established through credibility, dependability, confirmability, and transferability. Credibility was ensured by maintaining consistency in questioning, with peer debriefing and supervisor review used to enhance credibility and reduce researcher bias.

Data were collected through in-depth interviews. Prior to data collection, ethical clearance was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of Al-Hikmah University. Each participant signed written informed consent, including permission to audio-record interviews. Interviews were conducted face-to-face in quiet, private locations within the university at times convenient for participants. Each interview lasted approximately 20-30 minutes. With consent, interviews were audio-recorded and supplemented with manual field notes. Recordings were transcribed verbatim, and all transcripts were anonymized.

Data were analysed using Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step thematic analysis framework. Audio recordings were transcribed verbatim. Transcripts were then systematically analysed through familiarization with data, generating initial codes, searching for themes, reviewing themes, defining and naming themes, and producing the final report. Direct quotes from participants illustrated key themes while maintaining confidentiality through pseudonyms (P1-P17).

Ethical approval was obtained from the Research and Ethics Committee of Al-Hikmah University, Ilorin. All participants were fully informed about the study's purpose, objectives, and procedures. Participation was entirely voluntary. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Confidentiality and anonymity were maintained throughout. The study adhered to the Nigerian Data Protection Regulation (NDPR, 2019) in handling personal data.

Results

A total of 17 interviews were conducted and analysed. All interviews were completed successfully with no withdrawals. Seventeen female cleaners participated in the study. Ages ranged from 33 to 56 years, with most within the 35-50-year bracket. Work experience ranged between 10 months and 6 years, with the majority having worked for 2-4 years. Participants worked across hostels (53%), classrooms (12%), laboratories (6%), administrative blocks (18%), clinic (6%), and mosque (6%). Educational levels included no formal education (18%), primary education (53%), and secondary education (29%). All participants had served at least six months, meeting inclusion criteria.

Thematic analysis was employed following Braun and Clarke's (2006) six-step framework. Audio recordings were transcribed verbatim and read multiple times. Meaningful segments of text were coded manually. A total of 127 initial codes were generated across all 17 transcripts. Codes were grouped into potential themes, resulting in 8 preliminary themes. Themes were refined, resulting in 4 final major themes. Data collection continued until thematic saturation was achieved. To ensure confidentiality, pseudonyms (P1-P17) were used. Peer debriefing with the research supervisor enhanced credibility and minimized bias.

Knowledge of PPE Among Cleaners

All participants (100%) demonstrated clear understanding of PPE and its protective role. Most frequently mentioned items included gloves (100%), face masks (100%), gowns (94%), and boots (71%). Participants demonstrated task-specific knowledge: "I use nose mask for sweeping to protect me from fine dirt, and hand gloves protect me from germs while washing toilet, and boots for washing gutters" (P2). All participants attributed knowledge to monthly institutional training: "We receive training once a month in the auditorium" (P5). Participants articulated protective purposes: "Gloves protect my hands from germs and dirt" (P4), "The nose mask helps me not to breathe in dust and bad smells" (P3), "The gown protects my clothes and body from getting dirty and from germs" (P6), and "Boots protect my feet from dirty water and sharp objects" (P10).

Attitudes Toward PPE Use

Cleaners held overwhelmingly positive attitudes toward PPE. All 17 participants (100%) expressed favourable views. Representative quotes included: "Personally, I feel PPE is very important for me so I always use it for cleaning" (P2), "Personally I feel it is very important. Even if I'm at home I use PPE" (P4), and "I believe PPE is necessary. Without it, I would be exposing myself to danger" (P6). Some participants extended PPE use beyond workplace: "Even when I'm cleaning at home, I still wear gloves because I've learned how important they are" (P4). Despite environmental discomfort, perceived benefits outweighed barriers: "Nose mask prevents me from breathing. But I still use it" (P6), "Sometimes the mask makes it hard

to breathe, but I still wear it" (P17), and "The heat in this country is too much. When you wear all the PPE, you feel like you are suffocating. But we still try to manage" (P17).

PPE Practice and Compliance

Participants reported consistent daily PPE use for high-risk tasks: "I use it everyday because I wash toilet every day" (P2), "I use them always when working... I do not skip PPE use" (P4). Proper removal procedures were demonstrated: "I pull the left glove off, then gently move my hand to remove the right one. I wash my hands afterward" (P4), "I always use hand sanitizer" (P3). However, some reused disposable PPE: "I sometimes wash disposable gloves if it does not get torn or too dirty" (P8), "I always wash my gloves with soap before using them again the next day" (P15). Task-specific variation was observed: "I do not use gloves when sweeping but I use nose mask because of dust" (P2), while others stated: "No, I use them at all times even when sweeping" (P7).

Factors Influencing PPE Use

Individual factors included prior healthcare experience: "I have worked in the hospital before so I am used to using PPE" (P2), and personal injury incidents: "One time I cut my hand with broken glass when I was not wearing gloves. Since that day, I never forget to wear them" (P16). Institutional factors were strongest determinants. Monthly training: "We receive training once a month in the auditorium" (P5), "The management teaches us how to wear gloves well, when to change them, and how to wash them" (P10). Enforcement policies: "If I do not wear my gown, they will not allow me to work" (P4). Supply constraints: "Yes, the supply is enough but nose masks are not always enough for everyone" (P2), "Sometimes the nose masks given are not enough for everyone" (P5). Environmental challenges: "The heat in this country is too much. When you wear all the PPE, you feel like you are suffocating. But we still try to manage" (P17). Supervision through unannounced visits: "Yes, my supervisor comes to monitor us while we are cleaning. They do not inform us in advance, they just show up" (P2), "They come unannounced and lecture whoever is not using it" (P6).

Discussion

The study found that cleaners at Al-Hikmah University demonstrated strong knowledge and positive attitudes toward PPE, yet practice gaps remained due to supply limitations and task-based risk perception. All participants showed comprehensive understanding of PPE types, purposes, and applications, attributed to monthly institutional training sessions. This high level of knowledge aligns with the knowledge component of the KAP model and reflects positively on the university's training program. The finding that 100% of participants could identify basic PPE items and articulate their protective functions contrasts with studies from similar contexts where significant knowledge gaps were documented (Tolera et al., 2024; Gebreeyessus, 2022).

Knowledge gaps centered on selective use based on perceived contamination risk rather than fundamental lack of awareness. Some cleaners omitted gloves during outdoor sweeping while maintaining mask use for dust protection, suggesting informal risk assessment that contradicts universal precaution principles. This pattern mirrors findings from Ethiopian and Ugandan studies where workers demonstrated knowledge but applied it inconsistently based on visible hazards (Kigozi et al., 2024; Gebreeyessus, 2022).

Attitudes toward PPE were overwhelmingly positive, with all participants viewing it as essential and some extending use to their homes. This strong attitudinal foundation reflects high perceived benefits and susceptibility as conceptualized in the Health Belief Model. Participants clearly believed they were at risk, viewed potential consequences as serious, and trusted that PPE effectively protected them. The fact that perceived benefits outweighed

environmental barriers such as heat demonstrates robust attitude-behaviour alignment supported by institutional enforcement.

Practice patterns revealed both strengths and vulnerabilities. High compliance for toilet cleaning and waste handling demonstrated that workers recognized obvious hazards. Proper hand hygiene and PPE removal procedures showed successful skill transfer from training. However, reuse of disposable gloves and masks due to supply shortages represents a critical infection control breach. Similar adaptations to supply limitations have been documented across Nigerian healthcare and sanitation settings (Ilesanmi et al., 2023; Chiburoma, 2022).

The factors influencing PPE use operated at multiple levels. Individual factors such as prior healthcare experience and personal injury history enhanced motivation. Institutional factors emerged as strongest determinants: monthly training provided knowledge and reinforcement; organizational policies requiring PPE created non-negotiable expectations; unannounced supervisory monitoring maintained accountability. These findings align with occupational health literature emphasizing that sustainable behaviour change requires system-level interventions beyond individual education (ILO, 2022; OSHA, 2023).

From Neuman's Systems Model perspective, PPE functions as a flexible line of defence protecting cleaners from external stressors. The study revealed this defensive line is strengthened by institutional supports such as training and supervision. However, supply limitations and environmental challenges represent stressors that penetrate these defences, creating vulnerabilities.

Conclusion

The results carry significant implications for nursing education, practice, and administration. Nurses must recognize that occupational health advocacy extends beyond clinical settings to encompass all worker categories. Cleaners are essential partners in infection prevention and control, yet their safety needs are often marginalized. Nurses working in educational institutions should actively incorporate non-clinical staff into safety training, monitoring, and support systems.

Nursing curricula should include comprehensive content on occupational health for diverse worker populations, preparing future nurses to adopt inclusive approaches that value all workers' dignity and safety. Administratively, nurses can champion policies that ensure adequate PPE procurement, regular safety training, and effective monitoring systems. Nurses should develop culturally appropriate health education materials suited to workers with varying literacy levels.

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